

Metal Complexes of 2,4 (or 7)-Dimethyl Benzimidazole with Different Metal Ions Like Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II)

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The interaction between 2,4(or 7)-dimethyl benzimidazole with protons and different bivalent metal ions like Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) was studied potentiometrically at different temperatures, ionic strengths and in solutions of varying dielectric constant. The ionization constant of protonated species of 2,4(or 7)-dimethyl benzimidazole and the formation constants of complexes were computed by Bjerrum's method as adapted by Irving and Rossotti and compared with those of imidazole and other benzimidazoles. The validity of Amis equation was verified by plotting pK_a and $\log K$ of Cu(II) complex vs $1/D$, from which the distance of closest approach was calculated as 1.7 and 2.8 Å. The lower stability of DMBIm complexes, compared to imidazole, is attributed to the steric hindrance offered by the benzene ring of the benzimidazole.

LITERATURE reveals that no work has been reported on the complexing tendencies of 2,4(or 7)-dimethyl-benzimidazole (DMBIm) although the substituted benzimidazoles have been used as analytical reagents¹⁻³. The present paper describes the ionization constant of protonated DMBIm and the formation constants of the complexes of DMBIm with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) at different temperatures, ionic strengths and in solutions of varying dielectric constant. The dielectric constant of the medium was varied by varying the percentage of methanol in methanol-water mixture.

Experimental

DMBIm was prepared by the condensation of 3-methyl *ortho*phenylenediamine with glacial acetic acid in 4 *N* HCl⁴. The separation and purification of the compound was effected by column chromatography and purity of the compound was established by its m.p. The solutions of metal ions were prepared by dissolving required amounts of metal nitrates (AR grade) in CO₂ free double distilled water and the metal contents were estimated by titrating against standard EDTA (di-sodium salt) solution using suitable indicators⁵. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. An Elico digital pH meter, Model LI-120 with glass and calomel electrodes capable of reading ± 0.01 pH was used. The pH meter was standardised by using buffers of pH 4 and 9. Toshniwal high precision thermostat was used to maintain the temperature of the solution. The pH values in all aquo-organic mixtures were corrected by the method of Van Uitert and Haas⁶.

The experimental method consists of pH titration of the following sets of solutions (50 ml), maintained at different temperatures, against 0.2 *M* NaOH.

1. 3 ml 0.1 *M* HNO₃ + 5 ml 1 *M* KNO₃ + 30 ml methanol + 12 ml water.
2. 5 ml 0.1 *M* HNO₃ + 5 ml 0.04 *M* ligand in 100% methanol + 5 ml 1 *M* KNO₃ + 25 ml methanol + 10 ml water.
3. 5 ml 0.1 *M* HNO₃ + 5 ml 0.04 *M* ligand in 100% methanol + 1 ml 0.04 *M* metal + 5 ml 1 *M* KNO₃ + 25 ml methanol + 9 ml water.

The effect of ionic strength and solvent was studied by varying the volumes of potassium nitrate and methanol.

Results and Discussion

The protonated 2,4(or 7)-dimethyl benzimidazole (DMBIm) ionizes in solution as

The ionization constant of DMBIm was calculated using Irving-Rossotti method⁷ in 60% v/v methanol-water mixture at 35° and an ionic strength of 0.1 *M* KNO₃ and compared with those of certain other benzimidazoles and imidazole (Table 1). The pK_a

TABLE 1—IONIZATION CONSTANTS OF BENZIMIDAZOLES AND IMIDAZOLE AT 25° AND AN IONIC STRENGTH OF 0.1 *M* KNO₃

Compound	pK_a
Benzimidazole (BIm)	5.48*
4-Methyl benzimidazole (4-Methyl BIm)	5.67*
2-Methyl benzimidazole (2-Methyl BIm)	6.19*
2,4(or 7)-Dimethyl benzimidazole (DMBIm)	6.30
Imidazole (Im)	6.95*

* The values are taken from the paper H. M. JAFFER, *Chem. Revs.*, 1953, 53, 191.

values were also determined by varying one of the three parameters keeping the other two constant (Table 2). The accuracy of the values is of the order

TABLE 2—IONIZATION CONSTANTS OF 2,4-(or 7)-DIMETHYL BENZIMIDAZOLE AT DIFFERENT IONIC STRENGTHS, TEMPERATURES AND IN SOLUTIONS OF VARYING DIELECTRIC CONSTANT

Ionic strength	pK_a	Temp. °C	pK_a	Wt. percent of methanol	'D'	pK_a
0.04	6.03	25	6.20	25.29	63.87	6.17
0.07	6.07	30	6.14	34.50	59.83	6.15
0.10	6.10	35	6.10	44.13	55.61	6.13
0.14	6.14	40	5.98	54.23	51.19	6.10
0.18	6.17	45	5.90	64.83	46.56	6.04

of ± 0.05 . The order of pK_a values is BIm $<$ 4-methyl BIm $<$ 2-methyl BIm $<$ DMBIm $<$ Im. The decrease in acidity or increase in pK_a of methyl substituted benzimidazoles and imidazole can be explained as follows.

The introduction of a methyl group at 2- or 4-position in benzimidazole decreases the ionization of the protonated species due to hyperconjugative and inductive effects, respectively. As a result the pK_a values increase. The effect in terms of difference in pK_a values for methyl at 2-position (6.19-5.48) and 4-position (5.67-5.48) is 0.71 and 0.19, respectively. The presence of two methyl groups at 2- and 4-positions further decreases the ionization of the protonated species and the effect is additive. The experimental pK_a value, 6.30, is comparable with the expected value of 6.38 (5.48+0.71+0.19). The π -electron cloud associated with benzene portion attached to imidazole ring enables the nitrogen to withdraw the lone pair of electrons from proton more readily thereby increasing the ionization of protonated species. Hence the pK_a value is higher for imidazole when compared to benzimidazole.

It can be seen from Table 2 that the pK_a increases with increase in ionic strength of the medium. The small increase in pK_a may be due to secondary salt effect. The ΔH value 8.3 kcal mole⁻¹ obtained from the positive slope of the plot of pK_a vs $1/T$ is almost equal to that of imidazole (7.7 kcal mole⁻¹)⁸. The higher pK_a value for imidazole compared to DMBIm is, therefore, attributed to entropy effect (ΔS value at 35° for DMBIm is -0.2 e.u. whereas it is -6.0 e.u. for imidazole).

According to Coetzee and Ritchie⁹, the ionization constant in aqueous medium $K_{a(1)}$ and partially aqueous medium $K_{a(2)}$ are related by the equation

$$K_{a(2)} = K_{a(1)} \frac{\gamma_{HA^+}}{\gamma_{H^+} \gamma_A}$$

where ' γ ' is the activity coefficient of the subscript species in a partially aqueous medium relative to that in a pure one. In the present case, since $K_{a(2)}$ is found to be higher than $K_{a(1)}$, the ratio $\gamma_{HA^+}/\gamma_{H^+} \gamma_A$ should increase with increase in proportion of the organic solvent.

It is known that the electrostatic effect resulting from the change in dielectric constant of the medium will operate on the activity coefficients of the charged species only, its magnitude being inversely proportional to the radius of the ionic species under consideration. Consequently, the magnitude of this effect on the proton exceeds that on the acid HA^+ . Therefore, a decrease in the activity coefficients of the charged species with increase in proportion of the organic solvent is indicated. The validity of Amis equation¹⁰ was tested by plotting pK_a vs $1/D$ which gave a straight line from which the distance of closest approach r_0 was calculated as 1.7 Å. The protonated form of the ligand, DMBIm coordinates with the bivalent metal ion with the liberation of a proton which can be represented as

The metal-ligand stability constants of the complexes of DMBIm with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) were calculated using Irving and Rossotti method⁷ in 60% methanol-water (v/v) mixture at 35° and an ionic strength of 0.1 M KNO₃. Typical titration curves for the proton-ligand and [Cu(II)]-ligand systems are shown in Fig. 1. The values of \bar{n} and pA were calculated in the pH range of 5 to 6. The formation curve constructed by plotting \bar{n} vs pA attained the maxima at $\bar{n} < 1$ indicating the formation of 1 : 1 complexes in all the cases. The stability

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves.
I. Free acid
II. Free acid + DMBIm
III. Free acid + DMBIm + Cu(II)

constants were evaluated using pointwise calculation method. The uncertainty in log K is in the order of ± 0.05 .

According to Debye-Hückel equation the stability constant of the metal complex (log K) increases with increase in ionic strength if the interacting species are ions of the same sign, decreases if they are of oppositely charged ones, and remains constant if one of them is a dipole. The slight increase in log K values in all the metal complexes (Table 3) with increase in ionic strength is attributed to the secondary salt effect and suggests that the interaction is between the metal ion and neutral ligand.

TABLE 3—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL COMPLEXES OF DMBIm WITH DIFFERENT METAL IONS IN SOLUTIONS OF DIFFERENT IONIC STRENGTHS IN 60%v/v METHANOL-WATER MIXTURE AT 35° AND IN SOLUTIONS OF VARYING DIELECTRIC CONSTANT AT 35°, $\mu = 0.1 M$ KNO₃

Metal ion	Ionic strength (M)				Dielectric constant			
	0.04	0.10	0.18	0.26	68.85	59.83	55.61	51.19
Co(II)	3.02	3.11	3.26	3.27	—	—	—	—
Ni(II)	3.06	3.16	3.31	3.41	—	—	—	—
Cu(II)	3.10	3.21	3.34	3.47	3.21	3.05	2.90	2.74

The stability constants were determined at 25, 30, 35 and 40° (Table 4) at a constant ionic strength

TABLE 4—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL COMPLEXES OF DMBIm WITH DIFFERENT METAL IONS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES IN 60% v/v METHANOL-WATER MIXTURE AT AN IONIC STRENGTH OF 0.1 M KNO₃

Metal ion	Temperature °C			
	25	30	35	40
Co(II)	3.28	3.20	3.11	3.02
Ni(II)	3.38	3.26	3.16	3.05
Cu(II)	3.45	3.30	3.21	3.06
Zn(II)	3.11	2.96	—	—

of 0.1 M KNO₃ in 60% methanol-water (v/v) mixture.

The stability constants were determined for Cu(II)-DMBIm complex in solutions of different dielectric constant (Table 3). The values indicate that the stability increases with increase in the proportion of the organic component. The distance of closest approach, r_0 , was calculated as 2.8 Å from the plot of log K vs 1/D using Amis equation¹⁰.

The order of stability constant of DMBIm with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) is Co(II) < Ni(II) < Cu(II) > Zn(II), which is in agreement with the Irving and William's order.

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